

ISic3024

I.Sicily inscription 3024

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

volcanic

Object

altar

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 22871

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332348

1. [ὁ δεῖνα τοῦ δεῖνος Εἴ]σιδι θεᾶι ἐπ ἦ [κόωι ἀνέθηκε].

2.

Edition: PHI336543

1. [Ἀρτέμ]ιδι θεᾶι γῆς.

2.

Edition: PHI334104

1. [— — —].ΙΔΙ θεᾶ[ι] γῆ ς

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645380
PHI 332348
PHI 336543
PHI 334104

Bibliography

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